

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: Dnmt3b.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of Dnmt3b as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

13 1. Pawlak, M. and Jaenisch, R., 2011. De novo DNA methylation by Dnmt3a and Dnmt3b is
14 dispensable for nuclear reprogramming of somatic cells to a pluripotent state. *Genes & development*,
15 25(10), pp.1035-1040.